

A Food System Conceptual Framework for the FoSSNet Project

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John Ingram, Monika Zurek, Anna Obernoster
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Executive summary

The FoSSNet (Food Systems Science Network) project aims to foster networks and transdisciplinary knowledge sharing and collaboration for transforming Europe's food systems outcomes. This deliverable addresses the first concept that needs to be described as part of FoSSNet: Food Systems. It provides food systems framework visual, analyses food systems conceptual frameworks (CFs), and outlines a FoSSNet CF to create a shared understanding of food systems and help identify intervention points for transforming food systems outcomes.

This deliverable explains the process through which the FoSSNet CF was developed. Guided discussions among project members and a literature review and analysis of existing food systems CFs were used for determining key food systems elements: drivers, activities/actors, outcomes and feedbacks.

We developed an interim CF by building on the CFs developed by Foresight4Food (2019) and FAO (2022), but also integrating additional elements identified through project discussions and literature review of published CFs (i.e. other aspects of food environments, and additional drivers and outcomes).

The interim CF is a flow model showing core food systems elements (drivers, actors, outcomes and feedbacks). It centres on actors within the core supply chain (producers, processors, retailers, consumers, waste managers, and transporters), since through adapting their activities, food systems actors will play a key role in transforming food systems outcomes.

The interim version of the FoSSNet CF was continued to be refined by the WP1 team in the time leading up to and including the first FoSSNet conference held on 25-27 March in Oxford, UK. In this way it provided the basis for discussions around food systems in general and the final CF more specifically. It also helped to determine which stakeholders need to be involved in FoSSNet, and helped identify potential leverage points for transforming food systems outcomes in Europe.

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Authors	John Ingram (University of Oxford)
	Monika Zurek (University of Oxford)
	Anna Obernoster (University of Oxford)

Reviewers (name & affiliation)	Technical review	Thom Achterbosch (Wageningen University)
	Technical review	Håkan Jonsson (Lund University)

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1 Introduction

The FoSSNet project sets out to strengthen and deepen academic networks which are an essential element of a new Knowledge and Innovation (K&I) governance structure for Europe's food system. This new structure is needed because the current K&I system in the European Research Area is seen as insufficient to address the emerging challenges of nourishing Europe in a healthy, sustainable and fair way.

One of the important elements of any K&I system is developing a set of clear definitions and conceptual frameworks describing the key concepts used across academics and stakeholder groups. In the FoSSNet project we need to develop a set of interrelated concepts around food systems and food system knowledge that need to work together and partly build on each other. These include, among others, definitions of:

- Food systems;
- Food System science;
- Food System transformation;
- Food (System) Knowledge & Innovation System (FOKIS)

In this report we focus on food systems definitions and descriptions, and briefly explain how we derived these. Food System Science, Food System Transformation and FOKIS concepts will be explored further in subsequent reports/deliverables.

The CF was initially refined after WP1/WP2 on-line and in-person workshops in July 2024. The derived CF was then presented as an interim product to wider project members and external experts in the First FoSSNet Conference in Oxford in March 2025 and discussed by four randomised breakout groups. Feedback was collected and analysed after the conference. The updated CF was then prepared, agreed with the FoSSNet Executive and shared across the project for use with further activities.

2 The purposes of a conceptual food systems framework for the project

Project members discussed several times the reasons for developing a Conceptual Framework describing a Food System and identified several purposes of the FoSSNet Food Systems Conceptual Framework (CF):

First, a clear CF of a food system is needed to help guide the project and the wider community of both academics and food system decision makers in describing the main

elements of a food system together with its boundaries. In this way, the CF can help to create a joint understanding and terminology for its users describing all parts of a food system together with how these parts relate to each other and how they should be called. The CF can thus also clarify what is not part of the food system and how a food system relates to other systems, such as the energy or the health care system.

Second, the CF has an internal purpose via description and boundary setting as the CF needs to provide a clear model that can be used as a common point of departure by all Work Packages involved in the FoSSNet project and to help implement the project tasks. The framework should be applicable and accessible across all disciplines involved in the project.

Third, the CF also needs to help communicate food system concepts and terminology to project external academics and food system stakeholders. A CF reflecting distinct disciplinary perspectives that relate to elements of the CF and eventually shared across academics and stakeholders will be crucial for guiding and harmonising discussions and devising actions towards transforming Europe's food systems towards better food system outcomes. The CF will thus help communicate the food systems science field to academics and stakeholders, using both words and diagrams. This will support knowledge exchange around food systems and current issues, while also providing the grounds for discussions around food systems change.

Fourth, the CF will also be crucial for supporting research as well as teaching and learning about food systems in Europe (and globally). A CF that describes food systems elements and the connections between them can serve as the basis for sharing and expanding upon food systems knowledge while also identifying key knowledge gaps in food system science.

Fifth, the CF should help to identify potential intervention points for food system transformation, both known as well as the ones that have not yet been considered in food systems research. It can thus also further debates around food systems and food system change, including around where the boundaries of food systems are drawn and the extent to which food systems CF can describe actual food systems processes and connections.

3 Developing the FoSSNet Food System Conceptual Framework

The Food System CF for the FoSSNet project was developed in several steps up to and including the First FoSSNet conference in March 2025, and subsequent refinement based conference feedback. The process up to date included both guided discussions

among project members as well as a literature review and analysis of existing food system CFs.

3.1 Project meetings

The CF development process was started during the project's Kick Off Meeting in Roskilde, DK, from 24-26 April 2024. Led by the Work Package 1 team from the University of Oxford, meeting participants discussed:

- Purpose: What should be the purpose(s) of the CF (internally and externally)?
- Framing: What worldviews (social/natural/other science) should be included in the development of the CF? Who will be the users of the CF?
- Boundary: What elements should be included in the CF, which ones not?

Project members agreed that a food system framework should identify and dynamically link food systems elements such as drivers, activities/actors, outcomes and feedbacks. Clearly identifying which elements are key parts of food systems and describing how they are linked will help to guide action towards food systems transformation and determine who needs to be involved in the FoSSNet network. The CF should also include both natural and social sciences views of all the different food system elements. In addition, it should support a number of purposes both within the project and for external stakeholders to the project (see Chapter 2).

In the Kick-off meeting, project members also reviewed around 30 food system CFs that different projects and organizations created over the last few years which can be found in scientific literature. The selection was based on work done by the EU H2020 FOSTER project for their deliverable D1.2 (Cuhls et al. 2024). The various frameworks helped project members to think through the elements to be included in the FoSSNet CF.

In an online meeting on 3 July 2024 members of the different WPs reviewed results of the Kick-off meeting and discussed a first set of existing frameworks to see if they would fit the needs of the project. Following this online workshop a second meeting was convened at the Vrije Universiteit in Amsterdam, NL on 18 July 2024. At this meeting project members from WPs 1, 2 and 3 discussed both a first draft of a FoSSNet CF based on the list of selected elements, and ideas from existing frameworks that would fit the different purposes discussed in the Kick-off meeting.

The interim CF was presented to wider project members and external experts in the First FoSSNet Conference in Oxford in March 2025 and discussed by four randomised breakout groups. Feedback was collected and analysed after the conference. The updated CF was then prepared, agreed with the FoSSNet Executive and shared across the project for use with further activities.

3.2 Literature review on food system conceptual frameworks

Before developing the CF model outlined in this deliverable, the WP1 University of Oxford team reviewed existing food systems CFs, which informed the current model and will continue to guide the review and development of the FoSSNet CF.

The WP1 team reviewed 28 food systems conceptual frameworks (CFs) which had been identified as part of work conducted by Cuhls et al (2024), using the following Horizon scanning criteria: “Food Systems Depictions”, “Food Systems Explanations”, “Food Systems Definitions”. We conducted a further review of published CFs and identified an additional 6 CFs relevant for this study. To be considered a full food systems framework for FoSSNet purposes, CFs needed to contain the following four components: drivers, food supply chain activities/actors (including at least production, distribution, and consumption), outcomes, and connections between food systems elements and feedbacks (drawing on Ericksen, 2008; Ingram, 2011). All these elements are necessary for describing interactions and processes in food systems, and for identifying intervention points that can transform food system outcomes.

Out of the 34 CFs analysed as part of this study, a total of 22 CFs met these inclusion criteria (Bukeviciute et al., 2009; Ericksen, 2008; FAO, 2014; FAO, 2019; FAO, 2022; Foresight4Food, 2019; Hilmi, 2014; HLPE, 2017; Ingram, 2011; Ingram and Thornton, 2022; Institute of Food Science and Technology and 3Keel, n.d.; CIAT, 2019; Lomax, 2018; Nourish Initiative, 2014; Parsons, Hawkes and Wells, 2019; ShiftN, 2011; TEEB, 2018; Vallejo-Rojas, Ravera, and Rivera-Ferre, 2015; van Berkum, Dengerink, and Ruben, 2018; Voglhuber-Slavinsky et al., 2021; Zurek et al., 2018). Ten CFs did not contain the elements needed to qualify as a full food systems framework but nevertheless contained information relevant to FoSSNet, such as more information on food environments, outcomes, or actors (FAO, 2018; Farming First, n.d.; Gustafson et al., 2014; Halberg and Westhoek, 2024; IPES Food, 2019; Mueller, 2015; Niles et al., 2017; Turner et al., 2018; von Braun et al., 2023; Wittman et al., 2016). Another two CFs (European Commission, 2023, and Proctor et al. 2018) did not qualify as food systems frameworks or contain other information relevant to this Deliverable and were excluded from the analysis.

In a next step the WP1 team developed two additional criteria to analyse the reviewed frameworks that met all the inclusion criteria. In a qualitative analysis the team compared frameworks to one another guided by two questions:

- 1) How many different types of elements and connections do the frameworks contain? (Complexity)
- 2) How clear is it who needs to do what to transform food systems activities? (Utility)

'Complexity', refers to how closely a CF captures food systems dynamics rather than only the number or granularity of food systems elements in the CFs. The more types of elements and connections between elements a CF includes, the higher the team rated its complexity. CFs would receive a lower complexity score if they only included the basic requirements needed to qualify as a food systems framework: drivers, activities, outcomes, and one feedback loop/ connection between elements. CFs' complexity would increase with the number of feedback loops/ connections and types of elements (i.e. food environments, scales, and wider social and ecological systems) they contain.

'Utility' is the value a CF has for identifying pathways to transforming food systems outcomes, showing which actors could adapt which food systems activity and/ or policy in the food system. Transforming food systems outcomes means changing them from a sub-optimal to a more optimal state, for instance from poor diets to better diets (Ingram & Thornton, 2022). Utility in this analysis does not assess whether each CF accomplishes its stated purpose. To be classified as higher utility, a CF needs to include clear intervention points, showing which actor needs to adapt which activity or food systems policy to transform food systems outcomes. A CF that only lists different actors and processes in the food systems without linking them to food systems activities would be lower in utility, since it does not contain clear intervention points.

With this analysis the team aims to contribute to the debate on identifying a range of interventions points for food system transformation. This investigation can then also help with better understanding the potential role of Food system science and an associated Food system knowledge system for food system change. The analysis has been submitted as a scientific publication.

4 The FoSSNet Food Systems Conceptual Framework

The following sections outline the process for identifying food systems elements required for the FoSSNet CF and give information on what is included in each element in section 4.1. Section 4.2 explains the elements of the FoSSNet more in depth and gives an example for using the FoSSNet CF for transforming food systems outcomes.

4.1 Key elements of the FoSSNet CF

A wide range of conceptual frameworks exist across food, energy and water systems. Energy system conceptual frameworks tend to combined different primary sources with centralised generation for delivery to society, while water system conceptual frameworks generally differentiate water uses between domestic, industry, agriculture and environment. Neither energy nor water conceptual frameworks where particularly

relevant for food system consideration as they do not differentiate the range of activities that are relevant to the food system value chain.

For developing the FoSSNet CF, we therefore drew on the 22 CFs identified in our review that contained all the necessary elements to qualify as food systems frameworks and drew on an additional 10 CFs that did not qualify as full food systems CFs, but nevertheless contained relevant information (i.e. giving examples for actors or more information on food environments). The current working model is mainly based on the CFs by Foresight4Food (2019) and FAO (2022), since they contained all the elements necessary to qualify as full food systems frameworks and were general enough to be relevant to a wide range of food systems contexts. Moreover, they captured the complexity of food systems more than CFs such as Parsons et al. (2019) and Lomax (2018), which give a more general overview of food systems without giving much information about how food systems elements are interlinked. At the same time, the CFs by Foresight4Food (2019) and FAO (2022) are relatively accessible, compared with much more complex CFs, such as ShiftN (2011). We also included elements from other CFs that are relevant for the FoSSNet CF (such as food environments), creating a CF based on FoSSNet objectives.

Basing the revised CF on these two well-acknowledged frameworks was also valuable as they showed a marked development on earlier CFs in the literature (e.g. Erickson 2008) by clearly differentiating different sorts of drivers and outcomes into different 'systems' (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The Foresight4Food and FAO CFs

Following more discussions across the project members involved in the Amsterdam meeting on 3 Oct 2024, an online meeting with all the leads of the different Work Packages was then held on 8 Oct 2024 to solicit their feedback on an emerging draft food system CF (Figure 2).

FoSSNet Conceptual Framework

Figure 2: Interim version of the CF

In the interim version of the CF we graphically included food environments as an integral element, as had already been included in other food systems CFs (i.e. HLPE, 2017). Even though they did not qualify as full food systems CFs, we also drew on the frameworks suggested by Ranganathan et al. (2016) and Turner et al. (2018), which both contained more information on food environments. However, we subsequently noted the importance of food environments as spanning the Social & Economic conditions and Food System conditions (see Figure 3 below). Furthermore, the now non-linear Activities pattern did not lend itself to the earlier graphical expression building up from left to right across the hitherto linear depiction.

Another point raised by project members was the need to include actors more explicitly in the CF. As a result, we renamed the core of the CF 'Actors & Activities'. 'Actors' refer to all human actors undertaking the core food systems activities (e.g. farmers, processors, retailers, etc).

We also included additional elements in the current FoSSNet CF that were not included in the Foresight4Food (2019) and FAO (2022) CFs but were identified as key parts of food systems in project meetings. Especially the role of culture and heritage had not been explicitly featured in neither the Foresight4Food nor the FAO CF. To remedy this, knowledge systems and cultural heritage were added as key drivers shaping food systems processes, and cultural heritage and community building as one of the social and economic outcomes.

Finally, to highlight that all outcomes included in the CF are neutral (i.e. health outcomes can be more positive or negative), we included the word "status" after each of the social and economic outcomes. We also changed the terms for drivers to be more

neutral where necessary (i.e. replacing “geopolitical instability” with “geopolitical processes/ context, and “climate change” with climate conditions”).

After incorporating all feedbacks, a designer working with the Oxford WP1 team was commissioned to design the current draft CF (Figure 2).

Figure 3: The FoSSNet Conceptual Framework

The CF depicts food systems as complex adaptive systems in which many human and non-human elements interact to transform inputs into outputs, or outcomes. Feedbacks between interconnected human and natural systems shape the behaviour and properties of the entire system, which therefore has high degrees of complexity, uncertainty, and adaptiveness. While the CF visualises food systems elements and the links between them, it is a simplified tool that does not model the “reality” of food systems (see Foresight4Food, 2019).

The key elements in the FoSSNet CF are drivers, actors, outcomes, and feedbacks (see Glossary). Drivers include indirect drivers, which influence food systems by shaping wider systems connected to the food system (i.e. population dynamics influence socioeconomic systems, which in turn shape food systems). Direct drivers, on the other hand, directly shape the behaviour of food system actors (i.e. what technology is available shapes the behaviour of food producers) (Zurek et al., 2018). In the CF, increasingly thick arrows between drivers in the environmental, social and economic, and food systems highlight that the additive interactions between indirect and direct drivers shape food system actors’ behaviours.

Figure 3 is therefore a graphical representation of the food system designed to facilitate discussions on food system dynamics, food system management and food system science. The core food system ‘activities’ (and their corresponding ‘actors’) are shown in the central circle with supporting services applying to them all. The thickness of the red arrows represents the relative amount of material flow between given activities. The arrows originating in the ‘drivers’ areas coalesce to indicate their integrative nature, while the arrows leading to the ‘outcome’ areas are independent of

each other but collectively all apply. The framework does not include spatial or time dimensions, nor power dynamics as these issues are very case specific. It therefore needs to be seen as a tool to help guide research and stakeholder discussions for given circumstances.

Scientists and other researchers are not explicitly identified in the CF as food system actors *per se* but the importance of Science & technology is explicit as a driver in the Food Systems conditions, and Knowledge Systems is explicit as a driver in the Social & Economic conditions. Further, researchers are implicitly included as part of 'Supporting services: Inputs' (of knowledge) and also as researchers of all the other drivers and outcomes.

The CF includes the institutional environment (such as laws and regulations or informal rules), as well as supporting services such as Inputs (including knowledge creation) and logistics, highlighting that these are needed for supporting core food systems actors and activities.

Outcomes refer to the outputs of food systems, which are shaped by the interactions between drivers and activities. The CF includes four main social and economic outcomes (food and nutrition security status, equity and fairness status, livelihoods and economic status, and cultural heritage and community building status). Food systems also affect environmental conditions, such as soil health and net GHG emissions.

Food systems outcomes feedback to indirect and direct food systems drivers, which in turn shape the food systems actors' behaviours and actions. For instance, the food and nutrition security status of a population (outcome) can impact demographics (indirect driver) which interacts with direct drivers (i.e. food prices) to shape the behaviour of food systems actors (i.e. producers), which in turn influences food systems outcomes.

To transform food systems outcomes from such sub-optimal states to more optimal states (i.e. food security and ecosystem stability), policy makers may use the CF to identify several direct leverage points. For instance, they may fund research in sustainable urban agricultural practices, support laws and regulations centring food security and environmental sustainability, and foster networks allowing for the creation and sharing on food systems knowledge. These interventions may incentivise food systems actors to change their behaviours, which would then lead to improved outcomes of the specific urban food system (i.e. higher food security and better soil health).

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, this deliverable has defined the FoSSNet concept (Food Systems) by describing the CF and how it was developed. Based on a review of published CFs and discussions with project members, we identified key food systems elements (drivers,

actors, outcomes, and feedbacks), which helps set boundaries around how to describe a food system. The CF also includes further elements that are important for the FoSSNet project (i.e. food environments, knowledge systems, and cultural heritage and community building status). This understanding of food systems will help the FoSSNet project as well as the wider food systems community identify what counts as a food system, the elements it needs to include, and how those elements relate to each other. The CF can also be used for communicating with a wide range of stakeholders about food systems in general.

In addition to describing food systems dynamics, the CF aims to help identify intervention points for helping core food systems actors adapt food systems activities, which is needed for ultimately transforming food systems outcomes. For example, food systems policy makers may be interested in making an urban food system more healthy and environmentally sustainable.

Transforming Europe's food systems outcomes will require a shared understanding of food systems and transdisciplinary collaboration for identifying intervention points for creating healthier, fairer, and more sustainable food systems. The knowledge exchange networks created through the FoSSNet project will be critical for achieving these goals. The CF presented in this deliverable will help to create a shared understanding of food systems and core actors involved and guide the identification of intervention points for transforming European food systems outcomes.

The radical rearrangement of the food system activities in the centre of revised CF is a marked departure from the traditional linear depiction of the activities, now being presented with greater connectivity between individual activities and centred on waste and surplus food managing. This rearrangement relates to the overall project's Theory of Change by providing researchers and other stakeholders with a comprehensive way of conceiving the food system to help guide discussions on policy and practise interventions.

The CF is not limited to any particular food systems context, however, and was designed to be general enough to be applicable to a wide range of contexts. It can be used by a wide range of stakeholders to identify the specific drivers, actors, and outcomes that they are interested in, and guide action towards transforming food systems outcomes across science, policy, and society.

Glossary

Food System Drivers: any factor which influences how food system actors undertake their activities.

Food System Activities: all activities which comprise, and interact with, the 'value chain' from primary production to consumption.

Food System Outcomes: emergent properties derived from to one or more food system activities.

Feedbacks: the way in which food system outcomes affect food system drivers.

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